

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF UHC OFFSHORE PLATFORMS FOR MUSSEL FARMING

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Abstract

This document proposes an innovative offshore structure for mussel farming (raft) made of Ultra-High Performance Fibre Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC, named in this document UHC), which aims to boost the competitiveness of this sector in Europe.

The traditional raft is made of wood, which has a reduced lifetime, requires constant maintenance and implies deforestation. In this project two types of UHC rafts are proposed to replace it. The first, called Formex® Mixta raft, has similar geometry than the wooden one, but replaces the primary and secondary beams by UHC, increasing significantly the durability of the most critical elements. The second is the Formex® Plus raft, which substitutes the wooden joists for UHC joists and integrates them within the secondary beams to create a flat raft that facilitates the work. This system also allows the farming in opened waters, which nowadays is not viable with wooden raft because of the pulling of the joists due to the intense swell. The Utility Model of Fiber-Reinforced Concrete rafts for mollusc farming was granted in March 2016, and it has been requested in France, Italy and Chile (in process of acceptance).

The document explains the properties of the material used (registered as Formex®), the laboratory testing required and the process of design of both models of the UHC raft, showing figures of the first two prototypes floated.

1. Introduction

In the period 2005-2015 the European mussel production has decreased by 16%, while it grew in the rest of the world by 20% [2]. Many EU farming regions almost didn't renovate and their competitiveness has declined. However, Europe has a mussel tradition and outstanding coastal conditions for its farming. In fact, Spain is the 3rd top world producer with a 45% of the EU mussels and directly employing 11,500 people. This document proposes an innovative offshore structure for mussel farming (raft) which aims to boost the competitiveness of this sector.

Mussel farming systems depend on the oceanic conditions and the traditions. In Spain, South Africa and the US the raft farming system can be found, being the predominant system in the first country.

Figure 1. Group of eucalyptus mussel farming rafts in O Grove, Ria de Arousa (Galicia, Spain). Photo: Lufort-RDC

The use of this material has three sets of negative consequences:

Economic: The structure has a highly uncertain lifetime, between 5 and 20 years. It needs periodic maintenance, requiring frequent investments for reparations. The partial or complete collapse of a raft implies a production shutdown with negative economic consequences.

Industrial: each wooden raft is built manually and inefficiently through a high-risk job in the inter-tidal zone using hammers and nails. The replacement of damaged elements is slow, complex, and risky.

Social/environmental: it implies intense deforestation, as the trees used to build each wooden raft prevent approximately 48 t of CO₂ from being captured yearly. Water pollution is caused by chemically maintaining products and the progressive decomposition of the wood.

2. The traditional wooden raft

A traditional wooden raft is a grid of 20 x 27 m (540 m²) formed generally by 4 to 6 main beams connected to 4 to 6 polyester-coated steel floaters, 11 secondary beams supported orthogonally on the main beams. It has wooden joists supported orthogonally on the secondary beams and separated a distance between 0.6 and 1 m, depending on the traditions of each region and the producer. The lightship weight of a wooden raft ranges between 40 and 65 t. The main geometrical parameters of the elements are:

nº	Element	Units per raft	Geometry	Depth (m)	Width (m)	Length (m)	Weight/unit
1	Steel floaters	4 to 6	Cylindrical	∅ 2 to 2.4	-	3.5 to 5.5	2.3 to 3.5 t
2	Primary beams	4 to 6	Square	0.35 to 0.4	0.35 to 0.4	20	1.9 to 2.5
3	Secondary beams	10 to 12	Square	0.25 to 0.35	0.25 to 0.35	27	1.3 to 2.6
4	joists	25 to 40	rectangular	0.07 to 0.1	0.08 to 0.12	20	0.12 to 0.2
5	Harvest	500 ropes	-	-	-	12 (rope)	Up to 80 t

Figure 2. Description of the main elements of the most common wooden raft. Photo: Lufort-RDC

The use of wood in these offshore structures has its origin in the beginning of century XX, when the wooden hull of the ships was used for that purpose. Besides its mechanical strength, wood fulfils the following requirements:

- Reduced weight: The smaller the weight of the structure, the smaller the investment in floaters.
- High flexibility: the lower the stiffness of the structure, the higher the adaptation to the swell, and the lower the pull out of the mussel due to the vertical displacement of the rope.
- Easiness to drill and connect elements, facilitating the assembling of the beams and joists that compose the raft.

Wood has been traditionally used as no other material was found combining this lightness, robustness, and flexibility to adapt to swells. In countries where farming is carried out in opened waters, less intensive systems are used, as in the raft the damages of the connections are too frequent due to the intensity of the swell, so the lifetime is too reduced. This shows that there was a clear need of a durable, reliable and sustainable raft for different water conditions. In 2014 the materials engineering firm RDC designed an offshore floating raft made of Ultra High Performance Fiber Reinforced Concrete. The company IDIFOR (founded by RDC with the Spanish precast concrete company Lufort) manufactured it for first time in 2016 and at this moment already four elements are floating in Spain.

3. UHC properties

3.1. What is UHC

According to [1], Ultra High Performance Fibre Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC, also called UHC) can be defined as a cementitious-based material which combines three of the most significant technological advances in concrete: (i) a compressive strength exceeding 150 MPa with ductile behavior, (ii) ductile tensile behavior thanks to the use of a high amount of fibers, (iii) a special selection of fine and ultra fine particles, which should be selected to maximize the packing density but also the selfcompactability in fresh state.

Figure 3: Production of UHC elements at IDIFOR plant. UHC during mixing (left); UHC during pouring (center); UHC in hardened state (right)

UHC provides also significant improvements in terms of toughness, crack width control, impact resistance, fatigue, concrete-steel bonding and durability. All these improvements lead to new possibilities in the design of the structures: (i) elements can be lighter, slenderer, and performed with an important reduction of volume used, ordinary reinforcement and workforce associated; (ii) structures have an improved durability and then, maintenance costs are significantly reduced. The lifetime of the structures is longer and the carbon footprint over the complete life cycle is smaller.

UHC is especially competitive for structures with difficult access for maintenance, in aggressive exposure environments, and structures where the reduction of self-weight has relevant benefits. In recent years, the number of applications where UHC has been used has increased progressively (footbridges, housing panels, urban furniture...). However, the number of offshore applications performed is reduced to very few applications in upstream oil and gas industry.

In order to guide engineers to the use and design with UHC, several international recommendations have been developed in the last years. The most relevant is the French, which has already become a standard [1]. Spanish recommendations are expected to be published at the end of 2017.

3.2. Formex® properties

The UHC used by IDIFOR to manufacture the offshore platforms is registered by the engineering firm RDC as Formex®. It fulfils the requirements stipulated by the French guidelines [1], which are also expected to be a reference in the upcoming Spanish recommendations elaborated by ACHE, the Spanish Association of Structural Concrete. These requirements are divided in:

Rheology:

- Despite it is not required; the guideline mentions that the mixtures are self-compacting.

Durability:

- Water porosity at 90 days lower than 9%
- Accelerated chloride ion diffusion coefficient at 90 days lower than $0.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/s
- Oxygen permeability at 90 days lower than $9 \cdot 10^{-19}$ m².

Strength:

- Direct tensile strength of the matrix greater than 7 MPa.
- At least 135 MPa of characteristic strength in cubic elements of 100 mm of size, as the Spanish recommendations indicate for UHC (150 MPa of average compressive strength). For this parameter the French Norm establishes 150 MPa of characteristic compressive strength. Figure 4 shows the values of compressive strength obtained in the production of a raft in the spring of 2017.

Figure 4: Results of compressive strength of the batches performed in the spring of 2017 for the production of UHPFRC rafts in the context of this project

According with the classification methodology proposed for the Spanish recommendations of this UHPFRC can be defined as follows:

UHPFRC-135/CA/13/E3, SH-7/0.9/2/1

This classification implies that the material is defined as a material with a compressive strength in cylindrical sample of 135 MPa or 150 MPa in a cubic element of 100 mm of size. The term CA refers to the exposure class, and will depend on the project, not on the material properties. The following number refers to the maximum length of fibers used (13 mm in this case). Finally, the term E3 refers to a slump flow value according to EN 12350-8 between 750 and 850 mm.

Regarding tensile properties, it is said that a UHPFRC is SH when it presents a pseudo-plastic branch in tension with multi-micro cracking in the standard characterization test. Such is the case of the UHPFRC used in this project and in other precast elements performed before, which has a characteristic tensile strength of 7 MPa, with a hardening coefficient of 0.9, a peak strain of 2‰ and a crack opening at the intersection of the first softening line to the w axis of 1 mm. These values are presented in the characteristic tensile stress-strain and stress-crack opening law shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Characteristic tensile laws of the UHC used: stress-strain law to peak (left) and strain softening law stress-crack width (right)

Figure 6 shows the un-notched 4-point bending tests carried out to the UHC in 100x100x500 mm (L/h=4.5) beams used to precast the platforms. An inverse analysis specifically developed by López [3] was carried out to obtain the tensile stress-strain law of the material and verify its capacity to comply the tensile requirements.

Figure 6. Bending tests performed to 8 prisms of the UHC used in plant and average tensile stress-strain and stress-crack width laws obtained with inverse analysis

The use of this material for the development of the beams of the floating rafts has, compared to other construction materials, the following advantages:

- The high amount of steel fibres allows to remove the secondary shear reinforcement used in ordinary concrete structures. The extremely high compacity allows to reduce the geometric cover to 25 mm for passive reinforcements and 30 mm for the prestressing steel ensuring a minimum lifetime of 100 years for any exposure class. Both concepts allow a reduction of weight of 70% compared to a technically viable offshore platform made of ordinary concrete.
- The UHC does not suffer corrosion like the steel, and the coefficient of water penetration more than 10 times smaller than ordinary concretes, so water and oxygen cannot reach the prestressing steel during te service life.
- As it is inorganic, it does not decompose or get splinter as the wood. The UHC properties do not change with the moisture as the wood does, and neither with the effect of the sun, as many plastics.
- Compared to concrete, the average distance between cracks is reduced below 20 mm and crack opening under 50 microns in service. This value is admissible even for the most aggressive exposure classes defined at the Spanish Structural Concrete Instruction.

4. Design of UHPFRC rafts

The design of the elements that compose the raft was conditioned by the following aspects:

1. Design an element with similar surface than the wooden rafts, and with similar farming tools and equipment that those used nowadays.
2. Minimize the total weight of the structure and maintain the same floating system.
3. Minimize the number of different elements, in order to maximize the level of industrialization, favor the production of the precast elements and simplify the assembling.
4. The UHC beams should have a stiffness comparable to the wooden beams in order to avoid the pull-out of the mussels from the ropes.

Following these requirements, two different types of rafts were designed. The first (named Formex®Mixta raft) was developed to substitute the main and secondary wooden beams to enhance their durability. The wooden joists have been conserved from the traditional raft. The second and most advanced raft is the so-called Formex®Plus, which is completely made of UHC and which is conceived to provide a flat surface to facilitate the work of the farmers and is conceived as a structure that allows farming in opened waters.

The Utility Model of both fiber-reinforced concrete rafts for mollusc farming was granted in March 2016 (Publication no.: ES 1147609 U), and it has been requested for France, Italy and Chile.

4.1. Development of a durable standard UHC raft (Formex® Mixta)

The structural scheme of the raft is completely similar to the traditional wooden raft: The six primary beams are independent and connected to the six floaters, the 11 secondary beams are orthogonally connected to them with 22 mm of diameter steel bolts. The wooden joists are connected orthogonally on the secondary beams. In this model of raft, the main improvement of the use of UHC is the enhancement of durability of the structural beams.

In the traditional solution, the wood is screwed during the assembling process to do the connection. In UHC the screw has been avoided for the high concentration of prestressing steel. Instead, a notched cuboid element of polyethylene 1000 (density=1000 kg/m³) was emplaced in the formwork before the fabrication of the precast beams (see figure 7). During the assembling of the raft, this element was drilled in the adequate location, providing a tolerance of ± 4 cm in each direction.

Figure 7: Connection system of the traditional wooden raft (left); connection system of the UHC raft (right)

As the structure has the same number of elements than the wooden raft, the design of a UHC beam with similar structural capacity than a wooden beam required to develop flexural tests of the wooden beams in laboratory.

The capacity of the wooden beams was tested in the Concrete Science and Technology Institute of the Universitat Politècnica de València. The beams were purchased from a company that assembles wooden rafts in Galicia. For each of the beams was carried out a flexural four-point bending test with a ratio span/depth=10 (see figure 8). The spans ranged between 3 m and 3.4 m and the sections of the eucalyptus beams between 300 x 300 mm and 340 x 340 mm, being similar to the elements used to build the traditional rafts. The beams were submitted to a process of water saturation during the previous 4 days to emulate the real conditions. Load was applied at a speed of 0.5 kN/s, and the load-deflection curve was measured (figure 8). The standard deviation between the results of the four wooden logs tested did not exceed 20%. On figure 8 can be seen the theoretical load-deflection curve of rectangular prestressed UHC beams with 25 cm of width and different depths. The theoretical load-deflection curve of the beams has been obtained considering the properties of the UHC indicated at section 3.2. As can be appreciated, the response of a 25x22.5 cm UHC beam is very similar to the obtained from the wooden beam both in capacity and deflection.

Figure 8. Four-point bending test of a eucalyptus wooden beam (left); bending response of a wooden element tested and theoretical response of prestressed UHC beams with different depths

The testing allowed to carry out an inverse analysis and obtain the properties of the wood logs used in rafts. This allowed to obtain the equivalent dimensions of UHC beams that are required to substitute the wooden beams of the traditional rafts. They are shown as follows:

Element	Wooden elements (typical values)		UHC elements with comparable behaviour	
	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)
Primary beams	0.35x0.35, 20 m	2.4	0.35x0.225, 20 m	Lighted. 3.1 t
Secondary beams	0.3x0.3, 27 m	2	0.25x0.225, 27 m	Lighted. 3.05 t
Total weight raft (without floaters)	44 t		59 t	

Thus, with UHC the total thickness of the raft beams is reduced from 0.65 m to 0.45 m. Figure 9 shows the primary and secondary UHC beams produced for the first Formex® Mixta raft. The upper surface is texturized to prevent slippage. Figure 10 shows the grid performed with the beams before the integration of the wooden joists.

Figure 9. Primary and secondary beams stored before assembling

Figure 10. Primary and secondary beams on the floaters during the assembling of the Formex® Mixta raft

Figure 11. Formex® Mixta raft assembled and floating with harvest in its final location (O Grove, Ria de Arousa, Galicia, Spain)

4.2. Development of a durable flat UHC raft for opened waters (Formex® Plus)

This solution is an improved design of the geometry of the traditional raft. It is conceived for especially aggressive swell conditions or/and to increase the productiveness of the sector. The main difference is that the raft is completely flat, its total depth is more reduced and it does not have wood, so the maintenance is minimum. The wooden joists of the Formex® Mixta are here integrated as UHC joists connecting the secondary beams, composing UHC frames (figure 12, right).

Figure 12. From left to right: Joists of the wooden raft, of the Formex® Mixta raft and of the Formex® Plus raft

The UHC joist was designed to provide the same capacity as the wooden joists. As the secondary beams, the wooden joists were submitted to flexural tests to evaluate their capacity in bending. Figure 13 shows the bending test carried out for two different joists with section 100 x 80 mm (width x depth) with a span of 2 m. The test was carried out until the capacity to carry load decreased under 70% of the maximum value reached without capacity to recover.

Figure 13 shows that the theoretical capacity of a reinforced UHC joist with a similar section (100 x 80 mm) is comparable with the capacity of a wooden joist. Thus, the dimensions of the UHC joists in the Formex® Plus rafts are similar to the wooden joists. The width is not reduced in the design because a reduction would imply a reduction of safety for the farmers walking on the structure.

Figure 13. Four-point bending test of a eucalyptus wooden joist (left) and bending response of the wooden joist during the testing (right)

It is clearly observed the size effect in the wooden elements, which equivalent flexural strength is higher for smaller elements because of the higher homogeneity of the material in reduced sections (figure 14). This shows that the use of UHC instead of wood is more interesting for bigger elements.

Figure 14. Equivalent bending moment of the wooden elements tested

The UHC joists have a weight 2.5 times higher than the wooden joists. However, their integration in a frame with the secondary beams has a main advantage in opened waters: The connection between beams is multiplied, avoiding the pulling of the joists in agitated swell conditions. In the traditional raft, the joists are wooden elements with a length of 6 meters, supported in four secondary beams (3 spans of 2 meters). In conditions of swell with short wave length, the difference in height of the couples of floaters imply a relevant curvature of the primary beams, which lead to a significant variation of the height of each secondary beam. This implies a progressive pulling of the joists, which are nailed to the supports (see figure 15) and also a shear stress in the joints that progressively develops a crack around the hole of the joist and parallel to its axis.

Figure 15. Progressive pulling of the nails of a wooden joist due to the effect of short wave lengths in opened waters

This effect can be observed in the locations where there is a frequent swell with the wavelength in the range of the span between the extreme floaters ($\lambda=10$ to 30 meters). The following figure shows the frequency of swell for the period 2005-2017 in the sea of Línea de la Concepción, in Cadiz Region, at the south of Spain (Hs vs Tp Table, SIMAR point 6072024, information obtained from www.puertos.es). As can be seen, during approximately 13% of the time there is swell of 1 m height and wavelength between 25 and 39 meters.

Efectiveness: 84.13% 2005-2017	Tp (s), frequency										TOTAL	
	≤ 1.0	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		> 10.0
Wave height (m)	λ (m), wave length											
	6	14	25	39	56	77	100	126	156	> 156		
≤ 0.5	---	0.047	15.036	28.336	7.281	6.591	2.99	1.446	0.703	0.874	0.256	63.56
1	---	---	0.179	5.665	7.136	4.883	3.118	1.257	0.264	0.131	0.083	22.716
1.5	---	---	---	0.037	1.193	2.484	2.365	1.285	0.331	0.05	0.048	7.794
2	---	---	---	---	0.008	0.452	1.157	0.933	0.3	0.049	0.025	2.923
2.5	---	---	---	---	---	0.006	0.314	0.682	0.378	0.106	0.002	1.489
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.015	0.226	0.287	0.124	0.002	0.654
3.5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.031	0.199	0.123	0.012	0.365
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.001	0.051	0.141	0.032	0.226
4.5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.007	0.059	0.059	0.125
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.016	0.079	0.094
> 5.0	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.004	0.05	0.054
TOTAL	---	0.047	15.215	34.038	15.619	14.416	9.959	5.861	2.521	1.676	0.648	100%

Figure 16. Frequency of swell in Línea de la Concepción, Cádiz (Spain). Opened waters

Very near to that point was located a wooden raft on November of 2008 to evaluate its performance in these conditions. After 4 months (February 2009, see [4]), most of the joists were pulled, demonstrating that mussel farming with the wooden raft in these opened waters was not viable.

Figure 17. Evolution of a raft during winter in front of the coasts of Línea de la Concepción, Cádiz, Spain

The production of a UHC frame that integrates 2 beams and the joists in a single piece avoids this mode of failure, allowing to carry out mussel farming with the Formex®Plus raft in this type of conditions.

This effect is negligible in most of the estuaries of Galicia region, where are present 95% of the Spanish rafts. The frequency of swell for the period 2000-2017 in buoy in front of Vigo, Galicia (Hs vs Tp Table, SIMAR point 3014010, information obtained from www.puertos.es) shows that 99% of the swell has a wave length over 50 meters, which implies that the curvature of the primary beams is reduced and the pulling effect of the joists is negligible. For that reasons, the wooden raft and the Formex®Mixta raft are viable in that conditions. However, the Formex®Plus can be used to farm in opened waters of the region to relieve the pressure of harvest in the estuaries.

Effectiveness: 94.34% 2000-2017	Tp (s), frequency										TOTAL	
	<=1.0	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 >10.0		
Wave height (m)	λ (m), wave length											
	6	14	25	39	56	77	100	126	156	>156		
<=0.5	---	---	0.026	0.116	0.263	0.705	2.242	5.021	7.019	7.428	12.128	34.946
1	---	---	---	0.022	0.12	0.254	0.692	1.652	3.318	6.076	21.547	33.681
1.5	---	---	---	---	0.01	0.097	0.249	0.529	0.738	1.294	11.665	14.582
2	---	---	---	---	---	0.009	0.096	0.326	0.429	0.667	6.099	7.627
2.5	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.007	0.094	0.23	0.35	3.096	3.776
3	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.015	0.088	0.181	1.771	2.056
3.5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.001	0.026	0.106	2.821	2.955
4	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.004	0.218	0.222
4.5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.088	0.089
5	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.04	0.04
> 5.0	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.025	0.025
TOTAL	---	---	0.026	0.138	0.393	1.065	3.285	7.639	11.848	16.108	59.498	100%

Figure 18. Frequency of swell in front of the coasts of Vigo, Spain

Other advantages of the integration of the joists between the secondary beams are:

- The assembling is much faster because of the reduction in number of elements to connect
- A completely flat surface is created, which increases the operational safety and allows installing platforms with rails that facilitate the work.

The design of the Formex®Plus also modifies the six primary beams (2 per floater) for three frames (1 per floater), connecting the primary beams to facilitate the assembling and to reduce the curvature of the secondary beams. The secondary beams are substituted by 5 secondary frames of 27 meters of length that are supported orthogonally on the primary frames and spaced 2 meters. In the spacing, three shorter frames with a similar width are placed and supported between the spacing of the 27 m-length frames (figure 19). The

total weight of this system is of 83 t. The following photos show the grid performed with the frames in a Formex®Plus prototype performed in Vasc Country (Spain). Its length dimensions are 27 x 13.2 m.

Figure 19. Process of assembling of a Formex®Plus raft

4.3. Modelization of the UHC raft design

The structural behaviour of the UHC was modeled as a grid with a finite elements program. In the model was introduced a distributed load to consider the ropes with mussel (0.19 kg/m, 200 kg per rope). The secondary beams are simply supported on the primary beams and the last are supported on 4 points on the floater.

The load cases considered for the Ultimate Limit State (coefficients of majority of 1.35 for permanent loads and 1.5 for variable loads) are shown as follows:

- 1) Service state with the joists and maximum load of molluscs submerged: Equivalent of 0.19 kN/m and 0.67 kN/m of secondary beam.
- 2) Launching of the raft to the water line: The raft is supposed to be raised from the four extreme floaters. The weight of the raft is considered to be without harvest.
- 3) Condition of intense swell with a wave covering a line of floaters: This implies the forces equivalent to the buoyancy that results with the increase of the draught of the raft from 1.58 m (without harvest) to 2.2 m (floaters completely sunken) (see figure 20).

Figure 20: Relation between draught and buoyancy of the Formex® Mixta raft

- 4) Condition of intense swell with a wave descending 1 meter and with a wave length in the range of 20-25 meters (0.02% of the cases according to the table shown at figure 17, point SIMAR 3014010)

The bending efforts (kN*m) obtained in the model are shown in the following table. The values of maximum strength are obtained not considering the cooperation of the fibers to the bending capacity, so the capacity of both types of beam is similar because the depth and number of prestressing cables are similar. The table shows how the model performed proves that the beams are adequate for this grid design.

	Type of beam	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Maximum strength of the beam
Positive bending stress	Primary beam	71.1	72.8	-	-164.3	+242.9 kN*m
Negative bending stress	Primary beam	-90.6	-117.5	-81.8	-	-242.9 kN*m
Positive bending stress	Secondary beam	10.8	61.9	99.6	-	+242.9 kN*m
Negative bending stress	Secondary beam	-13.0	-75.6	-	-107.6	-242.9 kN*m

5. References

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